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Fukuoka Datasets for Semantic Place Categorization

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Abstract

We present several multi-modal 3D datasets for the semantic categorization of places. In addition to 3D depth information, other modalities like RGB or reflectance images are included. The datasets include indoor and outdoor scenarios obtained in different locations in the city of Fukuoka in Japan. Outdoor place categories include forests, urban areas, indoor parkings, outdoor parkings, coast areas, and residential areas. Indoor place categories include corridors, offices, labs, study rooms, kitchens, and laboratories. Depth sensors include SICK laser range finders and RGB-D cameras on a mobile platform, and Velodyne and FARO LIDARS on a car. The data is available for downloading at http://robotics.ait.kyushu-u.ac.jp/kurazume/oscar/kyushu_datasets.

Keywords

place categorization, outdoor, indoor, 3D data, multi-modal data, mobile robotics

Introduction

One important capability for intelligent mobile robots consists on understanding their surroundings by identifying the type of place they are located at. This information can greatly improve other high levels tasks like communication with humans (Zender et al. (2008); Pronobis and Jensfelt (2012); Rosa et al. (2018)), search and exploration tasks (Aydemir et al. (2011); Stachniss et al. (2008)), decision making (Hang et al. (2017); Crespo et al. (2017)), high level representations of space (Luperto and Amigoni (2018)), and many others (Kostavelis and Gasteratos (2015)). Lately, semantic information about places is also applied to autonomous cars (Bernuy and Ruiz-del Solar (2017); Garg et al. (2018)).

This paper presents several datasets for place categorization tasks that contain indoor and outdoor place categories. Our datasets provide the following properties:

- Complete: It contains multi-modal high resolution panoramic depth images combined with other modalities like colour images or reflectance data (except for the indoor RGB images).
- Diverse: It contains several outdoor and indoor scenario datasets.
- Varied: Different datasets are obtained using different sensors modalities such as SICK lasers, Velodyne and FARO LIDARS, and RGB-D cameras.
- Different: All data was obtained in Japanese indoor and outdoor scenarios that differ from standard occidental ones.

Other related semantic place datasets are also available on the web. The indoor COLD dataset (Ullah et al. (2007)) provides images of indoor places at different times of the days in several European buildings. In comparison to this dataset, ours provides RGB-D images of indoor

Japanese datasets and also high resolution depth panoramic scans with reflectance information. The Stanford 2D-3D-Semantics dataset (Armeni et al. (2017)) contains dense 3D maps of complete indoor environments obtained using Matterport Camera with 4.5m range. Our indoor panoramic dataset is obtained in a similar way but using a SICK laser scan that has 80m range. In addition, the Robot@Home dataset (Ruiz-Sarmiento et al. (2017)) presents 3D indoor scenarios with annotated objects using a RGB-D camera. Our indoor dataset contains small RGB-D trajectories of indoor buildings and also high resolution static panoramic scans using laser sensors. Finally, our indoor datasets are thought for the specific problem of semantic place categorization. In addition, all our indoor scenarios are taken in Japanese buildings and thus they differ from the previous occidental datasets in style, structure and decoration.

The outdoor semantic dataset the Cityscapes dataset (Cordts et al. (2016)) presents frontal image views of a car driving through a city. On the other hand, our outdoor datasets contain high resolution multi-modal panoramic depth images that cover 360 degrees around the car. However, in order to obtain the high resolution images our car has to stop every 10 meters. In total we provide three different outdoor datasets,

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Figure 1. Setup of the car with the FARO sensor.

Figure 2. Locations in Fukuoka city, Japan for dense panoramic scans.

two in high resolution obtained with static sensors (SICK, Velodyne), and one in medium resolution (FARO) that includes trajectories. All datasets are available for downloading at http://robotics.ait.kyushu-u.ac.jp/kurazume/oscar/kyushu_datasets.

Panoramic Multi-Modal Outdoor Dataset

The outdoor multi-modal dataset consists of 650 static high resolution 3D point clouds panoramic scans obtained using a FARO Focus 3D laser mounted on a car. Panoramic depth information is synchronized with color images obtained with a Kodak PIXPRO SP360 camera, that was also mounted on the car (Fig. 1). Each panoramic scan is composed of three synchronized sensor modalities: depth, reflectance, and RGB color. The FARO Focus3D sensor has a maximum range of 150 meters and a field of view of 360 degrees horizontally, and 300 degrees vertically. Each panoramic scan has a resolution of 5140 1757 pixels with 0.07 degrees horizontal and 0.17 degrees vertical angular resolution. For each scan we moved the car 10-100 meters, stopped and took the full panoramic scan and color images. We repeated this process several times in each area. Point clouds were off-line synchronized with color images using the SCENE software provided by FARO. Each panoramic scan is represented using the PTX* format.

The 3D colour panoramic scans were obtained at six different place categories in Fukuoka city, Japan: indoor parking, outdoor parking, coast, forest, residential area, and urban area, as shown in the map of Fig. 2. Example

Figure 3. Example panoramic color scans. Left to right, top to bottom: coast, forest, indoor parking, outdoor parking, residential area, urban area.

Table 1. Panoramic Multi-Modal Outdoor Dataset

Category	Number of scans per set							Total
	Set1	Set2	Set3	Set4	Set5	Set6	Set7	
Indoor Par.	16	16	13	15	17	13	15	105
Outdoor Par.	15	17	16	15	15	14	16	108
Coast	14	14	16	12	17	14	16	103
Forest	16	16	17	18	16	16	17	116
Residential	14	16	14	15	16	15	16	106
Urban	16	17	16	16	15	16	16	112
Total	91	96	92	91	96	88	96	650

panoramic images are shown in Fig. 3. Each category contains 7 sets of panoramic images. Each set was obtained in a different place inside the same category. Table 1 summarizes the data. The complete dataset is available at http://robotics.ait.kyushu-u.ac.jp/kurazume/oscar/kyushu_datasets/outdoor_dense.html. The distribution of files in the dataset is as follows where names in [brackets] indicate variables:

```
[Category] # Directory
|
| # Directory containing partial color images
|---- [Category].[PlaceId]_Scan_[ScanId].partial
|
| # Depth Panoramic image.
| # Lighter colors indicate closer points.
|---- [Category].[PlaceId]_Scan_[ScanId].Dep.png
|
| # PTX file
|---- [Category].[PlaceId]_Scan_[ScanId].ptx
|
| # Reflectance image.
| # Lighter values indicate higher reflectance.
|---- [Category].[PlaceId]_Scan_[ScanId].Ref.png
|
| # Color Panoramic image.
|---- [Category].[PlaceId]_Scan_[ScanId].RGB.png
|
| # Sampled point cloud (1284x440).
|---- [Category].[PlaceId]_Scan_[ScanId]_low.ptx
```

Panoramic Sparse Outdoor Dataset

The sparse outdoor dataset contains a total of 34,200 3D panoramic scans obtained using a Velodyne HDL-32E

*<http://www.leica-geosystems.com/kb/?guid=5532D590-114C-43CD-A55F-FE79E5937CB2>

Figure 4. Top: Setup of the car with the Velodyne sensor. Bottom: Example panoramic scan in an urban environment

Figure 5. Locations in Fukuoka city, Japan, for sparse panoramic scans.

laser scanner sensor mounted on top of a car. This sensor contains a vertical field of view of 41.3 degrees ranging from 10.67 degrees to 30.67 degrees and a horizontal field of view of 360 degrees. Each panoramic 3D point cloud has a resolution of 322166 points, with horizontal angular resolution of 0.17 degrees and vertical angle resolution of 1.33 degrees. Scans were acquired at 2 Hz. In addition the dataset contains GPS information obtained by a Garmin GPS 18x LVC. This information is stored in NMEA 0183 format at a frequency of 2 Hz. GPS is synchronized with point clouds using timestamps. Finally, the dataset also includes panoramic colour images captured using Kodak PIXPRO SP360 camera. Each colour image covers 360 degrees and has a resolution of 16.36 Megapixels. Images were acquired 67 Hz. However, colour images are not synchronized with point cloud data and was used for as references only. Sensors were situated on top a car as shown in Fig. 4.

Each panoramic point cloud is stored using the Point Cloud Data (PCD) file format from the Point Cloud Library. GPS data is stored using the NMEA sentences (\$GPRMC). Images are store in BMP format.

The 3D panoramic scans were obtained at six different place categories in Fukuoka city, Japan: indoor parking,

Table 2. Panoramic Sparse Outdoor Dataset

Category	Number of scans per set										Total
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10	
Indoor Par.	520	357	274	873	583	343	466	592	344	428	4780
Outdoor Par.	874	579	388	370	477	536	581	563	460	617	5445
Coast	511	254	571	221	314	376	872	506	386	287	4298
Forest	440	824	980	707	730	720	439	311	797	531	6479
Residential	674	787	667	724	563	973	717	720	977	662	7464
Urban	490	572	587	487	410	566	712	565	606	739	5734
Total	3509	3373	3467	3382	3077	3514	3787	3257	3570	3264	34200

Figure 6. SICK laser scanner on a rotating platform.

outdoor parking, coast, forest, residential area, and urban area, as shown in the map in Fig. 5. Each category contains 10 sets each representing a trajectory. Each set was obtained in a different place inside the same category. Table 2 summarizes the data.

The complete dataset is available at http://robotics.ait.kyushu-u.ac.jp/kurazume/oscar/kyushu_datasets/outdoor_sparse.html. The distribution of files in the dataset is as follows where names in [brackets] indicate variables:

```
[Category] # Directory
|
| # Directory for GPS data
---- gps_data
| |
| | # GPS data
| | ----- [Category]_[set]_[frame]_gps.txt
|
| # Directory for images
---- img_data
| |
| | # Image data
| | ----- [Category]_[set]_[frame]_[timestamp].bmp
|
| # Directory for point clouds
---- pcd_data
| |
| | # Point cloud files
| | ----- [Category]_[set]_[frame].pcd
```

Panoramic Laser Outdoor Dataset

This data consists of panoramic point clouds obtained using a SICK LMS-151 laser scanner on a rotating base as shown in Fig. 6. The panoramic point clouds contains depth and reflectance information. The point clouds have a resolution of 3750 3755x760 pixels with a vertical field of view of

Figure 7. Example panoramic scans taken with a SICK laser. Top to bottom: forest, residential area, parking lot, and urban area.

Table 3. Panoramic Laser Outdoor Dataset

Category	Number of scans per set							Total
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	
Forest	4	2	3	6	7	6	8	36
Residential	5	5	4	4	13	0	0	31
Parking	6	6	8	8	4	0	0	32
Urban	5	5	5	7	8	6	8	44
Total	20	18	20	25	32	12	16	143

Figure 8. SICK laser partial scans.

-85 105 degrees, and an horizontal field of view of 360 degrees.

Each panoramic image is represented using PTS format, where each point in the body contains its 3D-coordinates and the corresponding reflectance value inside the range [0-1]. Example panoramic scans are shown in Fig. 7.

The 3D panoramic scans were obtained at 4 different place categories in Fukuoka city, Japan: forest, residential area, parking lot, and urban area. Each category contains 7 sets of panoramic images. Each set was obtained in a different place inside the same category. Table 3 summarizes the data.

Panoramic Laser Indoor Dataset

This indoor dataset consists of panoramic point clouds obtained using a SICK LMS-151 laser scanner on a rotating base (Fig. 6) The point clouds contains depth and reflectance information. The point clouds have a resolution

Table 4. Panoramic Laser Indoor Dataset

Category	Number of scans per set				Total
	Set 1	Set 2	Set 3	Set 4	
Corridor	15	15	15	15	60
Kitchen	15	15	15	15	60
Laboratory	15	15	15	15	60
Study Room	15	15	15	15	60
Office	15	15	15	15	60
Total	75	75	75	75	60

of 3750 3755x760 pixels with a vertical field of view of -85 105 degrees, and an horizontal field of view of 360 degrees. Each depth panoramic image is represented using a matrix of 760 x 3750 3755 depth values in a .txt file. In addition, the corresponding grey scale image is provided in PPM format. The corresponding reflectance image is stored also in PPM format.

Partial scans of both, depth and reflectance data, are also provided in similar formats. The size of partial scans is 624 x 760 points. Partial scans S_i were obtained by dividing the panoramic scan. Partial scans overlap in 107 pixels (with corresponds to approx. 10 degrees) as shown in Fig 8.

The 3D panoramic scans were obtained at 5 different indoor place categories inside buildings at Fukuoka city, Japan: corridor, kitchen, laboratory, study room, and study room. Each category contains 4 sets of panoramic images. Each set was obtained in a different place inside the same category. Table 4 summarizes the data.

Data is stored using the following directory and files structure, where names in [brackets] indicate variables:

```
[Category] # Directory
|
-- [PlaceId] # Directory
|
| # Depth
-- [scanId]_depth.txt
|
| # Depth
-- [scanId]_depth.ppm
|
| # Reflectance
-- [scanId]_ref.txt
|
| # Reflectance
-- [scanId]_ref.ppm
|
| # Directory with
| #Depth Partial Scans
-- [PlaceId]_set_depth
|
| | # Depth (TXT)
| | -- depth_image[scanId]_depth.txt
| |
| | # Depth (PPM)
| | -- depth_image[scanId]_depth.ppm
|
| # Directory with
| # Reflectance Partial Scans
--- [PlaceId]_set_reflectance
|
| # Reflectance (TXT)
-- reflectance_image[scanId].txt
|
| # reflectance (PNG)
--reflectance_image[scanId].png
```


Figure 9. Colour and depth images from a laboratory.

RGB-D Indoor Dataset

This indoor dataset consists of RGB-D images taken by a Kinect Camera on a rotating base at a height of 125 cm. The Kinect sensor has 43 degrees vertical by 57 degrees horizontal field of view. And a depth sensor range of 1.2m - 3.5m. Example RGB-D images are shown in Fig. 9

Each depth image is represented by a 480 x 640 matrix of depth data in a .txt file, with undefined values represented by NaN. In addition a grey scale image is provided where NaN values are represented by full black. Each corresponding RGB image stored in PNG format.

The RGB-D images were obtained at 6 different place categories in different buildings at Fukuoka, Japan. Categories include corridor, kitchen, office, study room, and toilet. Each category contains different sets of RGB-D images. Each set was obtained in a different place inside the same category.

Data is stored using the following directory and files structure, where names in [brackets] indicate variables:

```
[Category] # Directory
|
| # Directory with RGB-D images
--- [Building]_[FloorId]_[Category]_[PlaceId]
|
| # Depth (TXT)
--- depth_image[ImageId].txt
|
| # Depth (PNG)
--- depth_image[ImageId].png
|
| # RGB (PNG)
--- image[ImageId].png
```

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